

Title: Artificial Intelligence to rich Exascale: Optimization of the energy consumption of a High Performance Computing (HPC) system by using AI

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INTRODUCTION:

The technological challenges imposed by the Exascale pose the question of a permanent improvement of the resources management solutions of large scale computing systems. The issue of energy consumption is now at the heart of the concerns of computer centers.

HPC is stepping up Big Data and AI workloads, but AI could also improve HPC.

AIM:

To develop energy-efficient scheduling algorithms based on Machine/Deep Learning.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

An amelioration of a precedent study of the users' behavior on the Gaia supercomputer of the University of Luxembourg was conducted. A classification of their jobs' resources consumption using a 6 months log traces was performed with four different resource metrics. However, this study doesn't inform about the energy consumption of jobs which crucial to better schedule jobs energy-efficiently.

A similar work where energy consumption is considered as a metric is in progress.

Also, a time series analysis of the logs.

RESULTS:

The first study showed as expected 2 types of users on this platform: the high users with high resource consumption and the low users with low resource consumption for a given metric.

In the progressing work, a better knowledge of the jobs' resource consumption is expected.

This knowledge combines with a modification of traditional scheduling algorithms should give us energy-efficient algorithms. A first modification of the EASY Backfilling based on the first result is already energy-efficient.

CONCLUSIONS:

The first modification of the EASY Backfilling to become energy-efficient is already a big step on the road to Exascale and this shows that AI can help to drop barriers on this road.

KEYWORDS:

AI; Exascale; Energy Optimization ; HPC ; Scheduling

BIOGRAPHY:

Fallou Tall is a co-operative master student in Data Science at African Institute for Mathematical Sciences (AIMS-Senegal) as a MasterCard scholar. As a part of the co-operative program, he is doing his internship at Bull Atos technologies as Data Scientist, Junior HPC Application & Performance. He has a background in mathematics, Operations Research in particular.